

THE ROLE OF THEORY IN THE STUDY OF HISTORY.

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ANNOTATION . In this article , the analysis of history , its content , and the history b o ' yich a In innovation methods , scientific processes and the general public knowledge of science and technology . ' o y a l a ri Methodological points are discussed .

Keywords : Theory , function , method , knowledge , methodology, modeling , hypothesis , hypothesis , concept , empirical semantics ;

INTRODUCTION

A comprehensive development of the theory of history from a scientific, theoretical and philosophical point of view will be a solid basis for achieving positive results in the process of conducting scientific research in the field of history. About this , the researcher Borisnyov said the following words: "Izuchenie teoreticheskix problem istoricheskoy nauki, bessporno, priobretaet seychas vse bolee vajnoe znachenie v praktike podgotovki kadrov istorikov vysshey kvalificatsii " . It is possible to agree with the opinion of the researcher , naturally , the subject of historical research must have scientific-theoretical knowledge at a higher level than history. On the other hand, the existing gap and fragility in the theory of history is likely to affect the researcher's scientific research activities .

The main function of the theory is to explain a problem scientifically and practically. It is to express an opinion in advance in order to search for truth, laws, and reasons. Each scientific method is developed on the basis of a certain theory. The theory gives a comprehensive picture of the laws and serious relationships in science in the field of knowledge. Theoretical knowledge is systematized and materialized in practice. There is a similarity between the theory and the method. They will be interrelated. Sometimes the term "theory" or "theoretical" is used incorrectly by people to explain things that they have not personally tested or experienced. In such cases, it is semantically replaced by the concept of "hypothesis". The word "hypothetical" is replaced by the word "theoretical". In some cases, the validity of the theory can be doubted. In some cases, the credibility of a theory can be called into question by calling it a mere theory. Knowing that the idea has not even been tested. Consequently, the word theory is often contrasted with the word "practice. History, like other sciences, has its own theory. Theoretical aspects necessary for the formation of history as an independent science were formed in the 19th century. In the field of history, a number of theories have emerged that recognize history as a science. But there were also different mutually exclusive views on the theory of history . This led to various debates, and these debates continue to this day. We think this debate will continue. In order to research the theory of history from a historical-philosophical point of view, perform a comparative analysis of existing theories and form the ability to research and analyze their common aspects and specific features. will have positive significance for the researcher. Theoretically, having high knowledge and skills is a factor that guarantees a positive result of research. Researcher Novikov's opinion about this is

noteworthy: "Theoretical knowledge transforms the results obtained at the stage of empirical knowledge into a deeper generalization, reveals the essence of the first, second, etc. phenomena. the procedures and laws of emergence, development and change of the studied object". Therefore, the qualitatively high level of theoretical knowledge provides an opportunity for a deep generalization of scientific research, a detailed analysis of the genesis of the object being studied. Until now, it is a natural process that the level of scientific and theoretical knowledge of historians has a direct impact on the quality of their scientific research. Human thinking develops based on thinking. And thinking takes place on the basis of the study of some historical evidence that allows us to imagine a certain historical reality. Robin Collingwood states: "Historical thinking is an activity or a function of self-consciousness, a form of thought that belongs only to a mind that understands historical thinking." So, historical consciousness is formed on the basis of knowledge acquired to know the historical past. To develop historical thinking, to know generally accepted theories of historical development and the ability to use them in the study or analysis of historical development processes. will need to be formed. If a person does not have historical knowledge, he will not have historical observation and he will not have historical thinking. Various scientific and theoretical concepts are used in the science and methodology of history. The meaning of the concept is the Latin word for complex, system. A specific method of explanation, understanding, interpretation of views, a system of principles, evidence, phenomena related to a certain field. According to A. Alimova, "The task of the historical concept is to help us understand the modern world." Hegel initiated a new stage in the development of the theory of historical science in the theoretical and practical study of historical progress as distinguished from nature. "He is wrong to widen this gap by denying the doctrine of evolution." A. Alimova zealously defends the theory of evolution, and it is a unique feature of history that this historian recreates the thoughts and motives of those characters he is narrating in his thinking. It gives priority to the mind of the historian. The occurrence of any historical events in a sequence suggests that this is not a historical sequence, a sequence, when for the time being the activity, its motives, cannot be recreated in the mind of the historian. We support this view to a certain extent. Only if the historian has a mature level of historical knowledge and historical thinking, he can reconstruct the past history in his thinking to a certain extent . This opinion of ours is also controversial, and in this case, the comprehensive description and concepts of past history will depend only on the historian. According to E. Kholikov, the main driving force of the historical process is the mind. Hegel views this idea as follows: Whatever happens in history is done by the will of man, the historical process is shaped by the actions of men, and the will of man is in action. all that is outwardly expressed is his mind. According to E. Kholikov, the history of mankind is a manifestation of people's feelings. This does not mean that such experiences are controlled by the mind. Indeed, man always lives surrounded by passions. The passion that surrounds a person never leaves him and has a direct and constant influence on his activities and decisions. A. Alimov looks at passions as objects and explains that the history of humanity is made from them. On the one hand, human history is a spectacle of reason, which uses passion as a weapon to achieve its goals. A. Alimov's thoughts on human thinking deserve attention. The human mind is often thought to be far from rational thinking. Which is when a person's specific thinking occurs in relation to a specific specific situation. Agreeing with this concept, we can say the following opinion: Man always lives in a certain society, space and time. In the theory of history, the main attention is paid to the general problems of studying history

as a real reality (ontology) and to the study of history as knowledge (gnesology), depending on what happened. will be Therefore, it is impossible to analyze human thinking and activity outside of society. Collingwood agrees with Hegel's opinion and puts forward the following opinion: "Thinking does not develop as long as the person is in himself; it is always associated with a specific person and a specific situation, and every historical character in any historical situation is rational to the extent possible within that given situation can act to a greater extent, and anyone in his place cannot do a greater thing than him.' When we analyze the history of the past, in many cases, the activities of historical figures seem to us to be logically irrational, unimaginably destructive.

While recommending the need to analyze and then draw conclusions in the study of history, Beruni, dividing it into periods is to determine the specific aspects of each period and through this method to social life, personal believes that it is possible to give a relevant and reasonable assessment to society.

The development of historical knowledge has led to the fact that it is more and more understandable and lively, theoretically, to look at the methodology as a whole or at the same time react to one or another of its aspects. appearing perfected.

The methodology is formed on the basis of the philosophical theory of knowledge, sociology and historiography. Naturally, the issues of the theory of knowledge occupy the main place in this science, but the main attention cannot be focused on this, but theoretical knowledge should be perfected by the practice of historical research .

In this case, people adapt their passions and mental activities to the situation. Which only fulfills or fulfills the need that is relevant to the situation at hand. The entire history itself is the history of thought and shows us the development of thought. The historical process remains essentially a logical process. Historical transitions represent logical transitions in time. History is a different form of logic, in which the relation of logical passing and going is not replaced but temporarily enriched or reinforced as passing and going. It follows that action in history is never accidental, but necessary, and our knowledge of the historical process is never simple empiricism when we establish the necessity of this process.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion is in order. Therefore, it is necessary and appropriate for the research conducted to study the science of history to be scientifically and theoretically based, because the researcher's research will have certain scientific and theoretical foundations, and this research is conducted based on the basics. For this reason, a researcher or a teacher of history who is conducting research in the science of history must first of all know the theories that exist in the science of history and are recognized in world history. This ensures that the researcher has a high level of scientific and theoretical knowledge. In this article, we have presented several points that justify the role and importance of theory in the science of history.

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